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Ipsilateral fractures of femur and tibia treated with the Ilizarov apparatus – Our results

Ivica Lalic¹, Mirka Lukic³, Bosko Vukajlovic², Sanja Tomic⁴

¹ Orthopedics Department, Clinical Centre Of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia,

² Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia,

³ Department of Anesthesiology, Clinical Centre Of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia,

⁴ Department Of Rehabilitation, Institute Of Oncology Sremska Kamenica, Novi Sad, Serbia.

Abstract

Introduction: Ipsilateral fractures of the femur and tibia (floating knee), are a challenging problem to manage due to a fact that they may include combinations of diaphyseal, metaphyseal, and intra-articular parts of femur and tibia, and are often associated with soft tissue and vascular injuries. Stabilization and early mobilization of the patient produce best clinical outcomes. We present our experience and results with these type of fractures.

Material and methods: At the Clinic for Orthopedic Surgery and Traumatology, Clinical Center Vojvodina, we have treated 12 patients with floating knee from 2008 - 2012. The right leg was involved in 9 and left in 3 patients. There were 8 Type 1, 2 Type 2A and 2 Type 2B floating knee injuries (Blake & McBryde classification). Age structure consisted of 8 men and 4 women. The mechanism of injury was road traffic accident. From that amount 9 fractures were closed and 3 open. The average age was 36 years. All patients were walking full weight bearing on 4th postoperative day.

Results: Average duration of hospitalization was about 3 weeks. 11 patients (90%) united at both fracture sites, within average union in 10 months. According to the Karlstrom criteria the end results were: excellent in 6, good in 2, acceptable in 2 and poor in 2 cases. The complications were knee stiffness in 3, delayed union of tibia in 2 and superficial infection in 3 cases.

Conclusion: According to our experience transosseous osteosynthesis with the Ilizarov apparatus provides us with stabilization, early mobility and full weight bearing and manipulation of bone fragments with the device without large surgical incisions, with minimal risk of infections.

Key words: Ilizarov apparatus, transosseus osteosynthesis, floating knee.

Introduction

Ipsilateral fractures of femur and tibia are called „floating knee“ and often are a combination of diaphyseal, metaphyseal, and intra-articular parts of the same bones. (1,2). These types of fractures are often associated with soft tissue, vascular and nerve injuries (1,2). They are often caused by large energy force (traffic injuries), fall from heights (2) and firearms (3). Although the exact frequency of these fractures is unknown, their incidence is rising, due to population growth and increasing number of vehicles in traffic (3). So far published series were from 24 (13) to 89 patients (14), and the largest published series is 222 patients during the period of 11 years (4).

Different treatment types for these fractures are described in literature, inoperatively with cast (7,10,13,16), and operatively with nailing (1,8,9,10,16) plates (14,16) and external fixation (14,15,16). Each of these methods have their advantages and disadvantages. Non-operative treatment leads to angulation, limb shortening and complications due to prolonged stay in bed (3,5). Operative treatment provides early verticalisation and mobilisation but is followed by complications such as infections and false joints (1,2,5,6).

Considering small amount of published series and inconsistency of preferred treatment technique, aim of our work was to present the results and treatment options for fracture type “floating knee” using the Ilizarov apparatus based on our own sample of patients.

Material and methods

At the Clinic for Orthopedic Surgery and Traumatology, Clinical Center Vojvodina, we have treated 12 patients of average age 40,5 years (18-

63) with floating knee from 2008 – 2012 (Table 1). All injuries were sustained in road accidents. Four patients were drivers three as co-drivers, and one patient was injured as a passenger in the back seat. Three patients were injured in a fall from a motorcycle. All patients had undergone preoperative detailed anamnestic and clinical examination, X-rays in the front-back and side projection, CT, MRI (for insight into the soft tissues). Four patients had urgent angiography for suspected violation of major blood vessels. For the classification of these fractures, we used the classification of McBride & Blake (11) (Table 2) by which the Type 1 fracture includes femoral and tibial body, type 2A articular surface of the same bones, whereas in type 2B upper femur and tibial pilon. All open fractures, underwent preoperative primary surgical management, tetanus and antibiotic protection and metronidazole. Until definitive surgery all patients were on extension. All patients were operated in spinal or endotracheal anesthesia on extension table and under the control of X-ray, on average of 3 days (5-7) since the incident. The surgical technique consisted of infiltrating the needles through the safe zones above the knee and in lower leg with subsequent fixation of their semi-ring units and connecting the rings with spacers. In 9 patients we set 4, and in 5 two rings in order to stabilize the fracture and restore all the major

fragments of bone in anatomic position. All patients were allowed weight bearing of 20% of body weight 4-th postoperative day. Bandaging was done in hospital every third day, whereas in patients who have had open fractures, bandaging was done on every second day. In six patients, we were able to facilitate the mobility of the knee joint by placing the hinge mechanism between the femoral and tibial rings, allowing for constant, early movement of the knee joint, while one patient refused because of pain. All actions on the device in the form of tightening the pins and spacers and periodic removal of some rings (depending on X-ray and clinical examination), were performed daily in the hospital on average of three weeks, and then patients were followed radiographically in the polyclinics of the specialist. All patients, in the hospital, started early rehabilitation, exercise of adjacent joints, the use of magnetic therapy and a gradual increase in weight bearing, depending on the type of fracture. The average time of wearing the appliance was 4 (3-5) months. The device was removed in the specialist polyclinic with usage of parenteral analgesics. After removing the device we allowed successive increasement of weight bearing of 30% of body weight per week. Full weight bearing was reached after 7 months.

For the evaluation of functional results, we used Karlstrom criteria (12) (Table 3).

Table 1. Materials and methods

Number of patients	Sex structure	Age groups	Extremities	Fracture classification	Blake-McBryde classification
12	8 males	18 do 30 3 patients (25%)	Right leg - 9 pac.	9 closed fractures	8 Type 1
	4 females	30 do 40 4 patients (33%)	Left leg - 3 pac.	3 open fractures	2 Type 2A
		40 do 50 2 patients (17%)			2 Type 2B
		50 do 60 2 patients (17%)			
		Over 60 years 1 patient(8%)			

Table 2. Blake and McBryde classification for Floating Knee injuries

Type 1 – True floating knee	Fractures of femoral and tibial diaphysis
Type 2 – Variants of floating knee	Involves one or more joints
Type 2A	The knee joint alone is involved
Type 2B	Involves the hip or ankle joints

Table 3. Karlstrom criteria for functional assessment after management of floating knee injuries

Criterion	Excellent	Good	Acceptable	Poor
Symptoms from thigh or leg	None	Intermittent slight symptoms	More severe symptom impairing function	Considerable functional impairment: pain at rest
Symptoms from knee or ankle joint	None	Same as above	Same as above	Same as above
Walking ability	Unimpaired	Same as above	Walking distance restricted	Uses cane, crutch or other support
Work and sports	Same as before	Given up sport; work same as before	Change to less strenuous work	Permanent disability
Angulation, rotational deformity or both	0	< 10 degrees	10 – 20 degrees	> 20 degrees
Shortening	0	< 1 centimetre	1 – 3 centimetres	> 3 centimetres
Restricted joint mobility	0	< 10 degrees at ankle; < 20 degrees at hip, knee or both	10 – 20 degrees at ankle; 20 – 40 degrees at hip, knee or both	>20 degrees at ankle; >40 degrees at hip, knee or both

Results

11 patients (90%) had full sanation of both fracture sites with an average sanation time of approximately 6 months, while in one case (10%) we had pseudoarthrosis of the proximal part of tibia. According to Karlstrom criteria the final results were: excellent in 6, good in 2, acceptable in 2 and poor in 2 cases (Chart 1). Following complications were noted: limitation of knee bending in 3 cases (in one patient to 20 degrees in 2 to 23 degrees), extended sanation in 2 and superficial infection in 3 cases (Chart 2).

Discussion

So far published series were from 24 (13) to 89 patients (14), and the largest published serie is 222 patients during the period of 11 years (4).

Our serie was consisted of 12 patients with average age of 40,5 years (18-63). Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) treated 24 patients of average age 38 years (17-75). Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14) published serie consisted of 89 patients of average age 42,5 (15-70) years. Anoop Kumar et al. (15) described 42 patients of average age 22,5 years (15-30). R. D. Fraser et al. (16) published largest study of treatment and followup of 222 patients of average age 52 years (14-90).

Sex structure of or patients was made of 8 males and 4 females. Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) had 22 males and 2 females, Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14)

80 male i 9 female patients, Anoop Kumar et al. (15) 30 male and 12 female patients, R. D. Fraser et al. (16) 190 males and 32 females.

All injuries within our patients were sustained in road accidents. Four patients were drivers three as co-drivers, and one patient was injured as a passenger in the back seat. Three patients were injured in a fall from a motorcycle. Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) did not specify the mechanism of injury of their patients. Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14) listed 57 patients as injured drivers and 32 patients injured in a fall from a motorcycle. Anoop Kumar et al. (15) listed 30 injured as drivers, 5 as passengers, 2 were hit while crossing the road outside of a pedestrian crossing and 5 patients injured in falls from motorcycles. R. D. Fraser a et al. (16) described 78 injured drivers, 70 pedestrians and 74 motorcyclists.

We had 9 closed and 3 opened fractures, Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) 21 closed and 3 opened fractures, Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14) 34 closed and 55 opened fractures, Anoop Kumar et al. (15) 28 closed and 14 opened fractures, R. D. Fraser et al. (16) 160 closed and 62 opened fractures.

Within 4 patients we had lesions of the blood vessels and nerves, Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) 10, Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14) 25, Anoop Kumar et al. (15) 16, R. D. Fraser et al. (16) 80.

Huseyin Arslan et al (13) and Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14) had not listed cases of amputation, Anoop Kumar et al. (15) had 13 cases, R. D. Fraser et al. (16) listed 7. We did not have any cases of amputations.

In functional results according to the Kallstrom criteria (12) we had: 6 excellent, 2 good, 2 acceptable and 2 bad results. Huseyin Arslan et al. (13) 3 excellent, 9 good, 5 acceptable and 6 bad results. Hwan Tak Heei et al. (14): 12 excellent, 20 good, 28 acceptable and 29 bad results. Anoop Kumar et al. (15): 7 excellent, 14 good, 14 acceptable i 7 bad results. R. D. Fraser et al. (16): 3 excellent, 15 good, 30 acceptable i 15 bad results.

Surgical treatment is the method of choice in the treatment of these fractures (5). Internal fixation compared to conservative treatment has the advantage because it rarely leads to stiffening of the knee and limb shortening, and patients spend less time in the hospital and are less time off from work (6). Omer et al. treated these fractures conservatively and and surgically and found that the time required for the splicing was 8 weeks shorter when the fractures were treated surgically (7). Behr et al. in the treatment of these fractures used intramedullary nailing, with average time required for healing of the femur of 10.5 weeks and 18 weeks for tibia (8). Ostrum et al treated patients with retrograde nailing with an average healing time for femur of 14.7 weeks and of 23 weeks for tibia (9). Dwyer et al. concluded that surgical or conservative treatment of the tibia does not significantly affect the subsequent movement of the knee joint later on (10). Lundy and Johnson claim that surgical stabilization of these fractures prerequisites for early mobilization of patients thus giving the best results (1).

In the treatment of these fractures using Ilizarov apparatus we kept strictly to the following rules: accurate repositioning of fracture fragments, stable and adequate immobilization of the fracture, not causing any additional trauma in the pathological focus, preservation of vascularization and sources for reparative regeneration of bone tissue, gradually performing all manipulations, achieving a permanent immobilization through strained needles, early dosed limb load.

Using the Ilizarov apparatus provides optimal conditions for the formation of bone tissue, and establishment of the anatomical structure and functioning of extremities.

Conclusion

Good treatment tactic, stabilisation and early mobilisation of patients have the best clinical outcomes in treatment of „floating knee“ type of fractures. Transosseus osteosynthesis with the Ilizarov apparatus, provides us with stabilisation, early mobilisations and full weight bearing, as well as manipulation of bone fragments with the apparatus without making large surgical incisions with minimal risk of infection, which is why we consider it a method of choice in the treatment of these types of fractures.

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Corresponding Author

Ivica Lalic,
Orthopedics Department,
Clinical Centre Of Vojvodina,
Novi Sad,
Serbia,
E-mail: laleort021@gmail.com